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DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF GPS-GSM BASED TRACKING SYSTEM WITH GOOGLE MAP BASED MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

GPS is one of the technologies that are used in a huge number of applications today. One of the applications is tracking your vehicle and keeps regular monitoring on them. This tracking system can inform you the location and route travelled by vehicle, and that information can be observed from any other remote location. It also includes the web application that provides you exact location of target. This system enables us to track target in any weather conditions. This system uses GPS and GSM technologies. The paper includes the hardware part which comprises of GPS, GSM, Atmega microcontroller MAX 232, 16x2 LCD and software part is used for interfacing all the required modules and a web application is also developed at the client side. Main objective is to design a system that can be easily installed and to provide platform for further enhancement.

KEYWORDS

GPS, GSM, Tracking System.

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